

Delivery 2.3

Report on the Portuguese Aquaculture: Survey

Version 3

D2.3 - Report on the Portuguese Aquaculture: Survey

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1. Executive Summary

This document presents findings from an anonymous survey conducted to assess the perspectives of the general public and aquaculture producers on Portuguese aquaculture. The survey aimed to assess public opinions on the current state of aquaculture, the level of appreciation for cultured fish and shellfish, and identify key needs and gaps within the industry. Through targeted inquiries, valuable insights were gathered to inform about the prevailing sentiments and concerns surrounding Portuguese aquaculture.

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2. Introduction

An anonymous survey was carried out to assess the current status of Portuguese aquaculture and to gather insights from fish farmers and other individuals actively involved in the aquaculture industry. Our primary goal was two-fold: firstly: to improve our understanding of the challenges confronted by the aquaculture sector, enabling us to tailor specialized training programs to address specific needs, and to assess the public perception and appreciation of aquaculture products. The GRINNAQUA team sought to collect responses through an anonymous survey distributed at aquafarmers' and the general public seminars, respectively. Aquafarmers' seminars took place in Setúbal, Portugal, on May 26th and on November 3rd 2023, bringing together key stakeholders in Portuguese aquaculture. Organized by the Portuguese Aquaculture Association (*Associação Portuguesa de Aquacultores*), the event was attended by the Secretary of State for Fisheries. The seminar covered essential topics, including discussions on licensing activities, and featured technical lectures on fish and bivalve production. The survey aimed to capture valuable insights from participants during this significant event at national level. Additionally, and in an attempt to overcome difficulties in gathering feedback from the first workshop, direct contact was made with the main national fish producers, who we were previously unable to contact.

The 2023 Science Conversations Series (*Conversas com Ciência*), conducted by the Serralves Foundation in collaboration with the Interdisciplinary Centre for Marine and Environmental Research (CIIMAR), aims to commemorate notable events such as World Wetlands Day, World Water Day, European Maritime Day, World Oceans Day, World Habitat Day, and World Science Day for Peace and Development. These monthly discussions, held on Sunday mornings in Serralves Park, provide a platform for community engagement with science, offering an informal space to explore research studies conducted by CIIMAR researchers.

Surveys targeting fishermen and sellers are yet to be completed. Reaching out to fishermen has posed significant challenges due to various factors, including the dispersed nature of their work locations, fluctuating schedules dictated by weather and fishing conditions, and limited communication infrastructure in certain regions. Despite our diligent efforts, attempts to establish contact with fishermen's associations and cooperatives have been unsuccessful, likely due to logistical constraints or lack of responsiveness. These obstacles have impeded our ability to directly engage with the fishing community and gather essential information or seek collaboration for our project.

To address this challenge, we identified a crucial opportunity through the upcoming Aquafuture Spain conference in 2025. This premier aquaculture event hosts over 150 exhibitors from 24 countries, coming from all over the Iberian Peninsula, and draws 2,500 visitors, including

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fishermen, aquafarmers, and vendors. The conference covers a broad spectrum of topics in aquaculture, encompassing marine and freshwater aquaculture, mollusc cultivation, and algae farming. It provides ample opportunities to explore technological advancements and commercial prospects within the industry.

The scheduling conflicts arising from multiple concurrent meetings in 2023, such as those attended within the scope of GRINNAQUA (e.g., European Maritime Day '23) and progress meetings of related projects (IGNITION and Aquacombine), prevented our team from attending the 2023 edition of Aquafuture Spain. For the next edition, our team has already reserved a stand, and project talks are scheduled for Aquafuture Spain 2025, as the event will not take place in 2024. The Aquafuture Spain 2025 will be an excellent opportunity to showcase all activities developed in the framework of GRINNAQUA and in an attempt to increase industry engagement.

3. Surveying efforts

3.1. Aquaculture sector

During the seminars, participants were encouraged to share their experiences and perspectives through a survey, with a clear emphasis that none of the questions was mandatory. This valuable information was intended to guide us in developing targeted training content for future initiatives, and we aimed for active participation from the farming community to shape and enhance the future of Portuguese aquaculture.

On a first approach, the GRINNAQUA team prepared an online questionnaire. The team participated in the XXIII Aquaculture Seminar, on the 26th of May, where the project coordinator presented the project and incited the practitioners to contribute by responding to the survey. During the networking session, the team was able to have one-on-one conversations with the practitioners who overwhelmingly said responding to the questionnaire in the smartphone was not very user friendly but would be available to do it later. Though the team contacted the association to forward this request, no responses were obtained with this effort.

Participating in the XXIV Aquaculture Seminar, on the November 3rd the team chose a different approach, with the questionnaires in physical format. However, despite delivering several questionnaires, the team encountered challenges in garnering participant engagement. The limited response underscored the need for increased efforts to raise awareness among smaller producers, encouraging their active participation and engagement with the scientific community. To tackle the issue of low feedback, the Principal Investigator of the project, Benjamín Costas, adopted a direct approach. Going back to the online version of the survey, he personally reached

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out to the major players in the aquaculture industry. These companies are specifically engaged in the production of key species relevant to Portuguese and Southern European aquaculture, such as seabass, seabream, trout, and flatfish (turbot and sole). The objective was to encompass the largest Portuguese companies, recognizing their significant market contributions and acknowledging the considerable impact and constraints they face (see Appendix I, the survey is in Portuguese as it was targeted exclusively at Portuguese producers).

Ultimately, the team got a total of six filled surveys, and they primarily came from larger Portuguese producers. From the six responses, two responses came from the same bivalve producer and therefore, it was statistically irrelevant and thus, excluded. The team chose focusing on fish production (four filled surveys) when presenting the results. After excluding bivalve from total national aquaculture production, Portugal produced in 2020 a total of 7495 t, corresponding to the four main farmed fish species: European seabass, gilthead seabream, rainbow trout and turbot. Given that the four fish companies participating in the survey are the biggest aquaculture players in Portugal in what these species are concerned, data collected in these surveys represents approximately 85% of Portuguese fish production.

2.2 General public

As part of the 2023 Science Conversations Series held on Sunday mornings in the Serralves Park (Porto, Portugal), Sergio Fernández-Boo delivered a talk titled "Marine Bivalves Cultivation: Challenges for the Health of the Species." The cultivation of marine bivalves faces increasing challenges due to climate change, impacting immune and specific systems and leading to the emergence of diseases that adversely affect production. Fernández-Boo elucidated these challenges during the conversation, discussing how research can contribute to developing solutions. Taking advantage of this involvement with non-academic public, the participants (a total of fifteen attendees) were invited to contribute to our consumer survey. This survey was designed to receive consumer perspective on their preferences and worries about aquaculture products (see Appendix II, the survey is in Portuguese to make it accessible to all consumers).

4. Survey results

4.1. Aquaculture sector

The survey was completed by four main key players in Portuguese fish aquaculture, with three of them directly contacted by Benjamín Costas. The opinions gathered represent two companies

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specializing in flatfish (turbot and sole) and two others that focus on a broader range of fish species, including both marine and freshwater varieties (seabass, seabream, and trout). The responses obtained reflect the perspectives of these species, which are significant in the Portuguese aquaculture sector based on FAO data from 2021 – specifically, turbot (3,538 t, \$37,579,890 USD) and gilthead seabream (3,090 t, \$19,447,180 USD).

These species also contribute substantially to the European aquaculture industry, where the combined value of the top three species amounts to \$2,196,448,550 USD out of a total sector worth \$5,034,033,900 USD. These key European species include rainbow trout (193,265.74 t, \$831,915,220 USD), European seabass (96,647.35 t, \$693,148,150 USD), and gilthead seabream (103,130.18 t, \$671,385,190 USD). This collective value represents a significant portion of the overall sector, totalling \$2,196,448,550 USD within the \$5,034,033,900 USD European aquaculture industry.

The four Portuguese fish aquaculture companies use three distinctive systems, as depicted in Figure 1, one of the participants uses two distinct rearing systems (RAS and Open Circuit). One of these systems is the Recirculating Aquaculture System (RAS), characterized by its advanced and environmentally controlled approach that prioritizes water recycling and internal reuse over continuous discharge. In the RAS setup, water undergoes comprehensive treatment and filtration to eliminate waste and impurities before being recirculated back into the aquaculture tanks for reuse. This closed-loop system is intricately designed to uphold optimal water quality, temperature, and conditions for the cultivated aquatic species, exemplified by the flatfish companies in this context.

Additionally, the Open-System Aquaculture (Open circuit) method is employed in the cultivation of turbot, while Senegalese sole is reared in RAS systems. This approach involves drawing water from an external source, such as a river, lake, or ocean. The water is then circulated through the aquaculture facility to support the cultivation of fish or other aquatic organisms before being discharged back into the external water body. Open-system aquaculture is commonly implemented in traditional pond systems, cage culture, or raceways.

Another method adopted by a distinct company involves the use of cages (marine and fresh water) for seabream, seabass and trout aquaculture. The sea cages, also known as mariculture cages or offshore aquaculture cages in some cases, are strategically positioned structures in natural water bodies like oceans or seas. In the case of rainbow trout, cages are placed in large lakes or dams. They offer a controlled environment for the cultivation of aquatic organisms, allowing exposure to natural water conditions while ensuring the sustainability and efficiency of the aquaculture operation.

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Fig. 1. Number of responses to the question “What production system is used in your unit?”. Data from four companies where one was using two rearing systems: RAS and Open-circuit.

Three out of four companies operate with their own facilities for breeders, however, it is worth mentioning that this survey is predominantly based on data from the largest producers in Portugal. Though, the company specializing in seabass and seabream relies on external hatcheries and nurseries as sources to obtain juvenile fish, as illustrated in Figure 2. Interestingly, due to this reliance on external sources, the company emphasize this aspect as a constraint in the production process when responding to the fifth question.

Fig. 2. Number of responses to the question “Does your aquaculture have its own maternity?”

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Regarding the primary constraints in their production, the most prominently mentioned challenge was diseases and pathologies, followed closely by environmental factors. In the seabass and seabream industry, in addition to the previously mentioned constraints, there were added concerns about feed costs and the supply of juveniles. The origin of pathologies was identified as bacteria and parasites or a set of agents. On the other hand, the Senegalese sole industry emphasized the genetic basis as its core constraint. The gathered opinions also aimed to discern the companies' needs in terms of courses and training. Unsurprisingly, these needs align with their major constraints. Disease prevention and early detection of pathologies were highlighted by three out of the four companies. It is important to also highlight that all companies informed that their production is already covered by some vaccination plan. Notably, one company expressed the importance of training in data analysis as a useful tool for their operations.

3.2 General public – “Conversas com Ciência” Event at Serralves Foundation, 15th October 2023

Six attendees out of fifteen participated in the survey. These were seafood consumers from the North region of Portugal. Three out of the 6 participants were male, two were female and one did not disclose gender. All participants had higher education (university degree) or more, indicating a relatively well-educated sample.

When queried about the frequency of consuming marine products, the majority (4 out of 6 people) reported eating them several times per week, while 2 out of 6 people indicated consuming them at least once a week. In terms of employment status, all respondents held permanent jobs 4 out of 6 people, with 1 out of 6 people combining work and study, and the remaining 1 out of 6 people being full-time students.

Regarding the origin of marine product consumption, only three individuals reported consuming exclusively wild products, citing factors such as taste, texture, health benefits, or variety as the reasons behind their choice. In contrast, two participants preferred aquaculture fish primarily due to its typically lower price. One respondent indicated no preference between aquaculture and wild fish, with factors like price, freshness, variety, and presentation playing pivotal roles in decision-making.

Notably, five out of six participants emphasized the nutritional characteristics of aquaculture fish. Omega-3 fatty acids richness, mentioned by all respondents, were particularly highlighted, along with higher content in vitamins, mineral salts, and proteins. Interestingly, the student mentioned buying aquaculture fish solely based on price, without specifically mentioning any of the nutritional characteristics. Regarding the procurement of products, whether wild or from

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aquaculture, none of the respondents purchase fish at fish auctions/markets. Typically, they acquire fish from supermarkets, fish shops, or restaurants. Concerning the type of product, the majority of respondents (5 out of 6 people) purchase fresh products, followed by frozen (4 out of 6 people), and equally by fresh packaged fish (3 out of 6 people), dried, or canned fish (3 out of 6 people), with smoked fish being purchased by 2 out of 6 people of respondents.

Finally, when asked about their preferred marine products, those who favoured wild capture mentioned clams, oysters, mussels, salmon, seabass, seabream, and shrimp. On the other hand, those who chose aquaculture fish as their main option mostly consumed seabass, salmon, mussels, shrimp, and trout.

5. Future approach

The main goal of this initiative is to gather knowledge regarding the adopted production strategies, husbandry procedures, and the primary challenges related to animal health and disease management in aquaculture. It also aims to gather more information on consumer expectations and perspectives regarding marine products' offer in the Portuguese market. The exploratory approach presented in this report helped the team to reflect on new methodological approaches to improve data collection.

Recognizing the importance of representation, alternative approaches will be applied to increase the statistical power of the obtained results. Regarding the survey **targeting farmers**, the team will persist on direct and individual contact with producers, by direct emailing/phone call. Reaching out to **fishermen and sellers** has indeed presented challenges, too. However, our team's future approach will involve two key strategies. Firstly, we will capitalize on our presence at Aquafuture Spain 2025, where the GRINNAQUA team has already reserved a stand, and project talks are scheduled. This event serves as the largest technological, training, informative, and commercial gathering of the aquaculture sector in southern Europe, particularly within the Iberian Peninsula, attracting 2,500 visitors, including fishermen, aquaculture practitioners, and vendors. Secondly, we will also pursue direct contact with fishermen and sellers by visiting fish markets and local markets in person.

To gather information about **consumer's choices**, the GRINNAQUA team is also planning to take advantage of "CIIMAR's Open Day", September 2024, during which CIIMAR is visited by a large number of people (previous edition around 20 000 visitors). During the event, an appointed GRINNAQUA team will be equipped with tablets and will be directly contacting visitors, asking for their participation in answering the survey.

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The GRINNAQUA team will launch a new online survey to be widely distributed on social media. With a strong engagement through social media now established, not only within the project's own social media but also within the recently created A2S group's social media, this is now a feasible option. The focus will be on Instagram account, which is more engaged with the general public, as well as on Twitter (X) with a more academic scope, and finally on LinkedIn, involving both **industry, academia, and the general public**.

The survey results will be presented in the 4th GRINNAQUA Workshop (M28), and pertinent information will be deliberated in a dedicated session of the workshop. This session will be attended by both researchers and industry representatives, fostering collaborative discussions and knowledge exchange. Additionally, a position paper is anticipated as an outcome of this comprehensive task. The primary objective is to gather knowledge on the adopted production strategies, husbandry procedures, main bottlenecks related to animal health and management, and enhance the perception of the general public.

The Workshop is planned to take place at CIIMAR facilities, employing a hybrid format that combines in-person attendance with online accessibility through a meeting platform. This approach is designed to ensure inclusivity and widespread engagement. The event will be jointly organized by CIIMAR and the respective leading institution, working collaboratively to facilitate a seamless and productive workshop series.

6. Appendix I – Survey for aquafarmers

Constrangimentos na aquacultura

Nos projetos GRINNAQUA e IGNITION temos como objetivo compreender os constrangimentos da indústria da aquacultura de forma a oferecer formação especializada de acordo com as necessidades. Gostaríamos por isso que partilhassem a vossa experiência e perspetiva connosco, deixando claro que nenhuma das perguntas tem carácter obrigatório. Essa informação servirá para nos orientar na preparação de conteúdos formativos para ações futuras em que gostaríamos de contar com a vossa participação.

1. Qual o sistema de produção usado na sua unidade (Ex. tanques de terra, RAS, etc.)?

2. Qual o tipo de animal produzido (ex. peixe, bivalves...)?

3. Qual a espécie?

4. A sua aquacultura tem maternidade própria?

Sim

Não

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5. Quais os maiores constrangimentos a nível de produção (ex. doenças, base genética, fatores ambientais, alimentação)?

6. Se na pergunta anterior respondeu "doenças", qual a sua principal tipologia (bactérias, vírus, parasitas, fungos)?

7. A sua produção está abrangida por algum plano de vacinação?

8. Em que lhe seria mais útil receber formação (ex. prevenção de doenças, boas praticas, nutrição, tratamentos de doenças...)?

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7. Appendix II – Survey for consumers

Ciclo Conversas com Ciência

Cultivo de Bivalves Marinhos: Desafios para a saúde das espécies

Sérgio Fernandez-Boo

Serralves, 15 de outubro 2023

Nos projetos GRINNAQUA e IGNITION temos como objetivo compreender a perspetiva do consumidor sobre os produtos provenientes de aquacultura. Gostaríamos por isso que partilhassem a vossa opinião e experiência connosco. Essa informação servirá para nos orientar na preparação de conteúdos formativos para ações futuras em que gostaríamos de contar com a vossa participação.

Caraterização sociodemográfica

1. Idade

- Menor de 25 Entre 46 e 65
 Entre 26 e 35 Mais de 65
 Entre 36 e 45

2. Género

- Feminino Masculino
 Não binário

3. Escolaridade

- Escolaridade obrigatória
 Curso profissional
 Formação universitária
 Pós-graduação

4. Situação profissional

- Empregado
 Desempregado
 Estudante
 Reformado

5. Região onde habita

- Norte Algarve
 Centro Açores
 Lisboa e Vale do Tejo Madeira
 Alentejo Estrangeiro: _____

Informações sobre consumo

6. Com que frequência consome produtos marinhos

- Várias vezes por semana Uma vez por mês
 1 vez por semana Menos que mensalmente

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7. Quais os produtos marinhos que consome mais frequentemente?

- | | |
|----------------------------------|-----------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Dourada | <input type="checkbox"/> Linguado |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Robalo | <input type="checkbox"/> Camarão |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Salmão | <input type="checkbox"/> Ameijoas |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Truta | <input type="checkbox"/> Ostras |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Pregado | <input type="checkbox"/> Mexilhão |

8. Qual a origem dos produtos marinhos que prefere, e porquê?

- | | |
|--------------------------------------|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Aquacultura | <input type="checkbox"/> Preço |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Selvagem | <input type="checkbox"/> Apresentação |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Frescura | <input type="checkbox"/> Sabor e textura |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Variedade | <input type="checkbox"/> Opção mais saudável |

8.1. Se não consome produtos de aquacultura, especifique as razões

9. Quais as características nutricionais que considera mais vantajosas nos produtos de aquacultura?

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Desconheço | <input type="checkbox"/> Proteínas |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Vitaminas (ex. A, B, D, E) | <input type="checkbox"/> Ácidos gordos (ex. omega 3) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Sais Minerais (ex. cálcio, iodo, ferro, fósforo) | |

10. Onde costuma adquirir estes produtos?

- | | |
|---|---------------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Diretamente do pescador / lota | <input type="checkbox"/> Supermercado |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Peixaria | <input type="checkbox"/> Restaurante |

11. Que tipo de produto compra normalmente?

- | | |
|--|--------------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Fresco avulso | <input type="checkbox"/> Fumado |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Fresco embalado | <input type="checkbox"/> Seco |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Congelado | <input type="checkbox"/> Em conserva |

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8. Document Information

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